

7/9/2021 Tuesday

9h - 10h30	Kick - Off - Introduction of the Coaches - Design Sprint Dynamics - Program guidelines - Participant Introduction
10h30 - 10h45	Break
10h45 - 12h	Lecture: Designing a Circular Future
13h - 14h15	Workshop: Circularity Scan Tool Companies introduce themselves Schedule Friday meeting with the companies
14h15 - 14h30	Break
14h30 - 15h00	Lecture: Mapping the problem
15h00 - 17h00	Workshop: Breakout rooms

8/9/2021 Wednesday

9h - 9h30	MORNING BOOSTER
9h30 - 12h	Workshop: Mapping the Problem Short recap '15 + Does everybody understand the task at hand? Teams work in Breakout rooms
13h - 14h30	Lecture: Circular/ sustainable design and Additive Manufacturing
14h30 - 14h45	Break
14h45 - 15h30	Lecture: Sustainable AM from a materials perspective (plastics)
15h30 - 16h	Lecture: Sustainable AM from a materials perspective (metals)
16h - 16h15	Break
16h15 - 17h	Lecture: Ideation & Creativity

9/9/2021 Thursday

9h - 9h30	MORNING BOOSTER
9h30 - 9h45	EIT RM Academy presentation
9h45 - 11h	Lecture: Business models for a Circular Economy
11h - 12h	Workshop: Breakout rooms --> Teamwork/ consult the coaches
13h - 15h	Workshop: Intro Ideation & decision (by Nicola) (1 h) Breakout rooms --> Ideation (1 h)
15h - 15h15	Break
15h15 - 17h	Workshop: Decision (1 h) Online Wrap - Up off the day: plenary presentations and feedback (45 m)

10/9/2021 Friday

Morning	Feedback meetng with companies
16h30 - 18h	Keynote: Dr. Dirk Schöps cluster manager from REWIMET and Hyperion Robotics, Ashish Mohite